

Investigating Students' Work Team Engagement in Science Online Learning: The Role of Teachers' Interaction Attributes

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Abstract

There is a dearth of research focusing on the engagement of students in work teams in the context of distance learning. This research examined whether the quality of interaction as perceived by the BSED-Science students significantly influences their work-team engagement in their science online learning classes during the academic school year 2021-2022. One hundred fifteen (115) Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Science students enrolled in private Catholic higher education institutions were selected through purposive sampling and completed a 2-part survey questionnaire online. This quantitative nonexperimental study employed weighted mean, standard deviation, and simple linear regression to analyse the survey data. Data revealed that these college students had a very high level of quality interaction with their science instructors online and work-team engagement. Furthermore, the quality of interaction as perceived by the BSED-Science students significantly influenced their work-team engagement in their science online learning classes. These findings suggest that maintaining consistent and wholesome interaction with students in their online science classes enhances their engagement in work teams. Therefore, teachers must strive to promote a positive online learning environment to intensify the engagement of students in work teams even if they are challenged due to the sudden shift of learning modality brought about by COVID-19.

Keywords: *quality of interaction; work-team engagement; science; online learning.*

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic, first identified in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, rapidly extended beyond health and economic sectors, profoundly disrupting educational systems worldwide (Tuga et al., 2022). In 2020, the pandemic introduced unprecedented challenges, affecting global and national socio-political, economic, and educational spheres (Cuaton, 2020). Higher education institutions (HEIs) faced widespread operational disruptions that hindered their contributions toward achieving

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Sustainable Development Goal 4 on quality education (Sonn et al., 2021). The impact on education from COVID-19 has surpassed that of previous pandemics or disasters in scale and severity (Wang & Sun, 2022). UNESCO reports that nearly 130 countries enforced nationwide school closures, with others implementing regional closures, creating systemic pressures that many institutions struggled to address (Treve, 2021).

COVID-19 heavily disrupted educational activities worldwide (Leal Filho et al., 2022). UNESCO data shows that higher education institutions and schools in 185 countries closed, affecting around 9.8 million African students enrolled in HEIs (Tamrat et al., 2020). Compared to what public higher education institutions have, private higher education institutions, especially those with limited resources, experienced educational challenges during this global health crisis (Khawaja et al., 2022). An example of this is some of the private higher education institutions in Oman, wherein they encountered equivalent difficulties, echoing the struggles of institutions globally during the pandemic (Magd et al., 2021). In fact, the pandemic also transformed higher education systems in Southeast Asia, where institutions faced a range of new challenges (Khan & Anwar, 2021).

In Spring 2020, 90% of higher education institutions in the United States cancelled in-person instruction, transitioning to emergency remote teaching due to the COVID-19 pandemic (Lederman, 2020). This rapid shift to online teaching affected nearly every aspect of students' lives globally (Plakhotnik et al., 2021). During this time, students encountered numerous personal and academic challenges (Wester et al., 2021). Alongside issues accessing appropriate technology for remote education, many students struggled with home environments that were not conducive to focused learning, often facing disturbances and distractions (Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021). True enough, two weeks into the lockdown and with the sudden shift to online education, 75% of students in Norway reported that their lives became more complicated, and 50% felt that learning outcomes would be harder (Almendingen et al., 2021).

Researchers have actively examined how students respond to disruptions in education in the wake of COVID-19 (Fox et al., 2020). In science online learning, Indonesian teachers faced challenges motivating students to participate, noting a general lack of enthusiasm among students. Teachers also struggled to help students grasp science lessons effectively in the online format (Ambawati et al., 2021). Studies in chemistry education revealed that students often lost motivation and engagement following the shift to online learning (Perets et al., 2020; Petillion & McNeil, 2020). In remote learning settings, students found it challenging to write laboratory reports without having conducted experiments themselves (Dickson-Karn, 2020). Due to the change in learning modality, aside from student engagement being put at risk, the quality of their learning and development, especially in specializations that require hands-on learning, such as anatomy, is stunted, and this brings lasting impact (Franchi, 2020).

In the Philippines, teachers and students were both vulnerable to the challenges brought by COVID-19, particularly due to the shift to distance learning (Lapitan Jr et al., 2021). For instance, medical students encountered numerous barriers—technological, personal, domestic, institutional, and community-related—as they adapted to online learning (Baticulon et al., 2021). Considering the shift to remote learning, many Filipino students struggled particularly with applying scientific concepts to solve problems, especially when these concepts required practical demonstration to validate their scientific effects (Rebucas, 2022). The same challenge has been observed in private higher education institutions in Davao City, Philippines. Collectively, there are challenges to online teaching and learning for students, teachers, and higher

education institutions; though these are deemed difficult, they can eventually be overcome (Guidote Jr., 2020).

Despite the wealth of research on COVID-19's impact on higher education, there remains a significant gap in studies focusing on its effects within developing countries like the Philippines. Much of the existing literature has concentrated on developed nations, particularly in the USA and Europe (Johnson et al., 2020; Wotto, 2020). Research related to addressing student engagement in the field of science remains scarce despite student engagement receiving considerable attention over the years (Schmidt et al., 2018). Recent studies revealed that student engagement in virtual teaching is of lower quality compared to face-to-face teaching (Dibner, 2020; Lan & Hew, 2020). With distance learning as the new normal learning modality, it has been revealed that home settings for online learning may not support optimal learning conditions (El-Sayad et al., 2021). Therefore, there is a need to conduct a study that will closely examine the engagement of students in online learning, considering that their engagement is another critical concern in online learning (Baloran et al., 2021).

Considering that the educational landscape is constantly changing, investigating how college students adapt to online learning during a global health crisis is essential for fostering positive student outcomes. Intending to provide valuable insights for higher education institutions to better evaluate online learning success, this study investigates whether the interaction attributes showed by science teachers virtually influence work-team engagement among Bachelor of Secondary Education students specializing in science at selected Catholic private institutions in Davao, Philippines. The study aimed to address the following three research objectives:

1. To determine the level of science teacher interaction attributes in science online learning as perceived by the BSED-Science students.
2. To determine the level of work team engagement among BSED-Science students.
3. To examine whether perceived science teacher interaction attributes influence BSED-Science students' engagement in work teams during online science classes.

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative nonexperimental descriptive correlational design to examine how the quality of interaction influences work-team engagement among BSED-Science students. Correlational research allows for analyzing the relationship between two or more variables, typically involving a predictor and an outcome or criterion variable within the same group of participants (Lau, 2017). Numerical data collected through this approach were analysed with statistical tools, making this method suitable for examining the magnitude and direction of the association of the variables in the study, perceived quality of interaction, and work-team engagement among these students in online science learning.

The respondents in this study are 115 college students pursuing a Bachelor of Secondary Education majoring in Science at Catholic private institutions in Davao, Philippines. They were selected through purposive sampling from two schools in the Archdiocese of Davao, two from the Diocese of Tagum, and one from the Diocese of Mati. With the program that these students are pursuing, it was also reported by their instructors that these students were also tasked to perform group activities in some of

their major subjects. These students were also exposed to both synchronous and asynchronous online learning modalities. The experiences they have, particularly the interaction they were able to establish with their instructors or professors and the way how they are engaged in work teams in science online learning, are considered to be imperative for their academic journey and, most importantly, for their future teaching profession. Moreover, since students from various Catholic private higher education institutions were involved, this was done since this study also aimed to provide the current status quo of online science education during a global health crisis within this context.

This research used a two-part adapted and structured survey questionnaire that was administered through Google Forms. Part I is intended for the predictor variable, which is the quality of interaction between the science and teacher and the student; a 25-item researcher-made questionnaire was employed. It comes in five dimensions, with five items each: helping/friendly, understanding, certainty, satisfaction, and authority. Using a 5-point Likert Scale (5 – strongly agree, 4 – agree, 3 – neither agree nor disagree, 2 – disagree, and 1 – strongly disagree), respondents were able to indicate their responses. Moreover, Part II elicited information on students work team engagement in online learning using a 30-item modified questionnaire developed by Digamon and Cinches (2017). This part assessed how students engaged in their science online learning classes in work teams utilizing a 5-point Likert Scale (5 – strongly agree, 4 – agree, 3 – neither agree nor disagree, 2 – disagree, and 1 – strongly disagree). Work team engagement contained five dimensions with six items each: authentic engagement, strategic compliance, ritual compliance, conventional, and non-rebellion.

Some terminologies and indicators were modified in the work team engagement survey questionnaire in order for it to be relevant to the context of the study. Retreatism was changed to conventional, and rebellion was changed to non-rebellion. This modification made the survey more uniform and made it easier for respondents to interpret. This will also address any potential confusion that could arise from mixed positive and negative statements. The two-part survey questionnaire was examined in terms of its content validity, and subsequently, a pilot test was conducted involving 15 college students pursuing teacher education degrees specializing in the field of sciences. Face and content validation was done with the help of three experts in the field of science educational research and with a statistician. The comments and recommendations these experts contributed to improving the survey questionnaire were incorporated into the final version of the research tool. An overall face and content validity rating of 4.39 or very good was obtained.

Moreover, Cronbach's alpha was employed to examine the internal consistency of the indicators of each of the dimensions, adhering to a value of 0.70 as a sufficient index of reliability or internal consistency to ensure the instrument's reliability (Taber, 2018). The pilot test results for the quality of interaction dimensions were as follows: helping/friendly ($\alpha = 0.851$), understanding ($\alpha = 0.851$), certainty ($\alpha = 0.783$), satisfaction ($\alpha = 0.785$), and authority ($\alpha = 0.733$). A very high Cronbach's alpha, which indicated a high reliability, was obtained for the quality of interaction scale ($\alpha = .934$). On the other hand, the pilot test results for the work-team engagement dimensions were as follows: authentic engagement ($\alpha = 0.854$), strategic compliance ($\alpha = 0.723$), ritual compliance ($\alpha = 0.801$), conventional ($\alpha = 0.822$), and non-rebellion ($\alpha = 0.854$). Overall, the work team engagement also obtained a very high Cronbach's alpha value, which also indicated its high reliability for the construct being measured ($\alpha = 0.919$).

All indicators in each dimension of these two-part survey questionnaires were retained because they passed the threshold value for internal consistency assessment.

The researcher submitted the study for ethical clearance approval to the Holy Cross of Davao College Research Ethics Committee. With the approval from the institutional ethics review board, the researcher then emailed a formal request to conduct the study to selected Catholic private higher education institutions in Davao, Philippines. Upon approval, the researcher was introduced to a focal person at each institution who supported the study throughout the data-gathering phase. Before distributing the survey link, the researcher sought informed consent from participants to confirm their eligibility for the study. Respondents were consistently informed of their rights throughout the study. From time to time, the respondents are informed about their rights in this study. The researcher utilized a Google Form, which contained the 2-part survey questionnaire that was used to elicit the data necessary for the study. There was no time limit for filling out the survey e-form. With Google Forms' feature, a direct spreadsheet was utilized to collate the responses of the respondents. Access to the data that was gathered in this study was solely given to the researcher. It was kept with utmost confidentiality and was stored using the researcher's password-protected Google Drive.

The data gathered in this study were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics, particularly weighted mean and standard deviation, were utilized to assess the quality of interaction perceived by the BSED-Science students and their work team engagement. Inferential statistics, specifically simple linear regression, was used to determine whether the perceived quality of interaction significantly influences the work team engagement of the BSED-Science students.

Results

The results of the data gathered on the quality of interaction as perceived by the BSED-Science students and their work team engagement in science online learning are presented in this section. To begin, presented in Table 1 are the descriptive statistics on the level of quality of interaction as perceived by the BSED-Science students with its dimensions. The quality of interaction between science teachers and students, as perceived by the BSED-Science students, had a very high rating ($M = 4.25$, $SD = 0.74$). There are three dimensions that consistently obtained a very high rating: helping/friendly ($M = 4.26$, $SD = 0.69$), understanding ($M = 4.34$, $SD = 0.71$), and satisfaction ($M = 4.31$, $SD = 0.64$). On the contrary, two dimensions obtained a high rating: certainty ($M = 4.9$, $SD = 0.66$) and authority ($M = 4.17$, $SD = .74$).

Table 1. Means and Standard Deviations on the Measure of the Perceived Quality of Interaction Between Science Teachers and BSED-Science Students in an Online Learning Modality

<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Helping/Friendly	4.26	.69	Very High
Understanding	4.34	.71	Very High
Certainty	4.19	.66	High
Satisfaction	4.31	.64	Very High
Authority	4.17	.74	High
Overall Weighted Mean	4.25		Very High
Overall Standard Deviation		.62	

Table 2 presents a summary of the descriptive statistics on the level of the BSED-science students' work-team engagement. In general, the BSED-Science students are very engaged in work teams during their science online learning classes ($M = 4.33$, $SD = 0.65$). Notably, the conventional type of engagement earned the highest mean ($M = 4.45$, $SD = 0.62$), followed by ritual engagement ($M = 4.38$, $SD = 0.62$), strategic engagement ($M = 4.30$, $SD = 0.64$), non-rebellion engagement ($M = 4.29$, $SD = 0.65$), and lastly, authentic engagement ($M = 4.26$, $SD = 0.66$).

Table 2. Means and Standard Deviations on the Measure of the Work-Team Engagement Among BSED-Science Students in an Online Learning Modality

<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Authentic Engagement	4.26	0.66	Very High
Strategic Engagement	4.30	0.64	Very High
Ritual Engagement	4.38	0.62	Very High
Conventional Engagement	4.45	0.62	Very High
Non-Rebellion Engagement	4.29	0.65	Very High
Overall Weighted Mean	4.33		Very High
Overall Standard Deviation		0.45	

Table 3 shows the results of the regression analysis to determine whether the quality of interaction as perceived by the BSED-Science students significantly influences their work-team engagement in science online learning. A simple linear regression analysis using the enter method was performed to evaluate how the perceived quality of interaction among BSED-Science students predicts their work-team engagement during online science learning classes. The model showed statistical significance, $F(1, 113) = 125.520$, $p < 0.001$, indicating that perceived interaction quality plays an important role in predicting work-team engagement.

Table 3. Regression of Association Between Quality of Interaction Between Science Teachers and BSED-Science Students and their Work-Team Engagement

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Model 1</i>						
	<i>Unstandardized Coefficients</i>		<i>Standardized Coefficients</i>			<i>95% CI</i>	
	<i>B</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>LB</i>	<i>UB</i>
Constant	2.09	.20		10.323	0.000	1.69	2.49
Teacher's Interaction Attributes → Work-Team Engagement	.53	.05	.73	11.204	0.000	0.43	0.62

Note: $R = 0.725$; $R^2 = .53$, $df = 1, 113$; $F = 125.520$; $Sig. = 0.000$

Discussion

BSED-science students reported that their online science teachers were highly understanding. They perceived that their science teachers were approachable, considerate, and willing to clarify instructions, offer feedback, and guide them patiently through challenging areas in their online science classes. These teachers were able to provide the necessary guidance, instruction, encouragement, and meaningful feedback, for it is expected that in an online class set-up, the majority of the students are active,

and they also expect consideration (Seifert, 2021). Students also noticed that their teachers expressed genuine satisfaction in their achievements, showing trust and valuing their contributions. Part of this is encouraging creativity, promoting independence, and supporting group efforts. Darby (2019) found that creating a positive, encouraging atmosphere in online classes helps students feel more engaged and makes learning more enjoyable. In addition, when students receive deep appreciation, it can transform the learning environment into a place where they feel a sense of safety, trust, and openness (Weiss, 2000, as cited by Lee et al., 2021).

In addition, students felt their teachers were both friendly and helpful. Science teachers were able to maintain support, be approachable, and be reliable, and they often lit the mood of virtual classes with humor. They were also able to open their communication lines via social media platforms. This is truly beneficial for students, particularly in emergency remote teaching. Students get more comfortable with their online classes if they are getting enough support from their online teachers (Kulal & Nayak, 2020). However, students observed that their teachers demonstrated strong knowledge and authority, offering clear explanations and maintaining well-organized, goal-focused online classes. Fatani (2020) similarly found that students felt more satisfied with classes where instructors showed preparedness and encouraged active participation.

They also noted that their teachers balanced authority with approachability, maintaining standards that felt achievable, offering flexible deadlines, and promoting an environment where questions were welcomed. The result is consistent with the findings from the study of Lemay et al. (2021), wherein it was felt by college students in Northeastern North America that their teachers online are relaxed with their academic standards, such as grading, participation, attendance, deadlines, and the like. BSED-Science college students' interactions with their online science teachers left them with a wholesome experience. The wholesome approach seen in these private Catholic higher education institutions in Davao, Philippines, helped create a conducive online classroom. It has already been proven that teacher-student interaction has an impact on the satisfaction of students in online learning (Hasan & Khan, 2020). With this, it is important to foster wholesome student-teacher interaction online.

The high level of engagement demonstrated by BSED-Science students in their online work teams reveals a strong commitment to their tasks, especially through conventional engagement. In this type of engagement, the BSED science students stay fully involved in their group work; they show focus and confidence that the tasks contribute meaningfully to their skill development in science. Truly, when there is a strong student-to-student interaction in an online learning environment, this is an indication that engagement is manifested and, hence, must be valued (Martin & Bolliger, 2018). These students also practice a ritual type of engagement wherein they show their competence in collaborating and contributing actively to the objectives set by their groups. This is in consonance with what Stephens et al. (2017) stated: demonstrating the ability to collaborate effectively is essential for students. This further suggests that the BSED-Science students not only fulfill their duties and responsibilities individually but also cultivate a collaborative environment and facilitate meaningful learning that is beyond their individual objectives.

This might not be new for teachers teaching online or in person, but students show engagement in their online science classes strategically. It is strategic in the sense that they desire to finish their assignments or any tasks for the reason that they want to gain recognition, fortify their sense of belonging within their group, and, of course, have timely feedback. This strategic engagement, as demonstrated by the BSED-

Science students, confirmed the assertion of Kanellopoulou and Giannakoulopoulos (2020) that students engage in academic tasks not just intrinsically but also with extrinsic motives. Non-rebellion engagement further underscores their dedication; students consistently meet their responsibilities without defiance, supporting findings by Kwon et al. (2019), who associate task commitment in online settings with higher success rates. Finally, authentic engagement emerges when students find personal meaning in their tasks, prompting interest, creativity, and motivation to perform well, consistent with Dymont et al. (2020), who note increased online engagement in relevant and authentic activities. The very high engagement of BSED-Science students in work teams, as revealed in this study, affirmed the significance of student engagement in an online set-up and specifically as a collaborative community (Álvarez & Montes, 2021).

The study's main findings highlight the role of cultivating virtual interaction with students while showing desirable qualities, which, in turn, influences BSED-Science students' engagement within online work teams. As employees of a private Catholic higher education institution, these teachers displayed wholesome attributes that fostered a positive learning environment, which in turn encouraged students to participate actively and consistently in their group tasks. Research supports this influence, showing that students value teacher interactions as a vital part of their online experience (Wallace, 2003, as cited by Cole et al., 2021) and that a strong teaching presence positively impacts student engagement behaviors (Zhang et al., 2016). Moreover, desirable behaviors in teachers have been shown to be essential in nurturing student engagement (Cents-Boonstra et al., 2021), while teacher-student interactions are the most crucial element for sustaining student engagement in virtual settings (Wahid et al., 2020). Thus, the study's results strongly support and affirm Zhou's interaction Th. This finding accentuates the importance of teacher presence in creating a supportive, engaging, and effective online learning experience, which is especially consequential within the values-oriented framework as adhered to by most Catholic institutions.

Conclusion and Directions for Future Research

COVID-19 resulted in widespread changes to higher-level education, including the rapid transition of teaching to an online setting. Private Catholic higher education institutions in Davao, Philippines, along with other academic institutions globally, had to shift from face-to-face to emergency remote education. College students were compelled to study online, wherein most of them had limited access to facilities, and the majority encountered less contact with their classmates, peers, and teachers. This study explored whether the quality of interaction as perceived by the BSED-Science students significantly influences their work-team engagement in their online science classes. It was identified that teachers always show desirable qualities during their interaction with their students online. Moreover, students also reported that they are very engaged in their online science classes. Most importantly, the quality of interaction they have with their teacher significantly impacts their engagement in work teams in their online science classes. Future research should explore how these desirable teacher attributes influence other aspects of student success, including academic performance, retention, and satisfaction in online settings. Researchers could also examine the impact of specific teacher behaviors across different disciplines and institutions, both private and public, to generalize findings more widely. Future researchers must strive to provide empirical findings that will deepen everybody's understanding of how

cultural and institutional values, such as those in Catholic education, shape the engagement of students virtually and interaction as well.

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Conflict of Interests

The author states that the research was conducted without any commercial or financial ties that could lead to a conflict of interest. The author states that the research was conducted without any commercial or financial ties that could lead to a conflict of interest.

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